

POSITIVE EFFECTS OF DEBATE FOR LEARNERS

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ANNOTATION

Main goal of this article is to show effects of using debate in learning, pupils can easily avert being scared of communication in English. Moreover, if they practice regularly, they are able to boost up their pronunciation, fluency and vocabulary.

***Key words:** interactive methods, debate technique, real-life situations, persuasive speech, argumentative skills , practice skills, critical thinking abilities*

Introduction

The use of active and interactive technologies in the lessons of the English language increases interest in the subjects which are being studied, helps to improve the quality of education, and allows pupils to use various sources of information. The forms of embodiment of active teaching methods are diverse: discussions, brainstorming, and various conversations. Interactive methods include project activities, role-playing, debates and so forth.

When using an interactive strategy, the role of the teacher changes dramatically; he/she ceases to be central, defines the general direction, controls the time and order of fulfillment of work plans, helps in case of serious difficulties. At the same time, pupils need to jointly solve assigned tasks, overcome conflicts, and find common ground. It is also essential for interactive methods that there is interdependence between group tasks, and the results of their work complement each other. One of the most effective forms of implementing an interactive strategy is the Debate technology.

Methodology

According to the doctor of pedagogical sciences E.O. Galitsky, debate is a form of communicative training, a way of organizing schoolchildren in educational work, which allows you to train independent work skills with literature and other sources of information, develops the ability to conduct a discussion and defends his/her own point of view, taking into account the fact that the opposite position also has a right to exist. [1] It should be noted that technology “debate” might be used in EFL lessons as a device make students’ practice skills of English Language in real-life situations. Krieger comments: “Debate is an excellent activity for language learners. This is owing to the fact that it engrosses students in a broad range of cognitive and linguistic ways. To add to providing meaningful speaking, writing and listening practice, debate is also highly efficient for developing argumentative skills for persuasive speech and writing.” [2]

Data collection and Analysis

Debate is an educational technology, an interactive form of vocational training, based on independent work of students, which within the framework of the intellectual game format contributes to the systematization and formation of knowledge, skills necessary for professional development of students. Debate is a competition of words and arguments, formal discussion of a topic in accordance with certain rules. [3] It is a technique that activates mental human activity and creativity, defend his/her point of view. Debate feature is that they allow the parties to better understand each other's positions. [4]

It should be also mentioned that in an EFL setting, where language learners might have inadequate possibilities for practicing English in real-life situations, debating opens up chances for them in order for expressing their opinions to use the language with common sense. This is a single practice in which pupils need to use all English skills along with skills in presentation, delivery and vocabulary building. Makiko Ebata puts it: “Learners are required to confidently express their thoughts when learning a new language for global communication in order for students to be vocal, critical thinking skills are essential. The use of debate has been an effective technique for

improving my students' speaking and critical thinking abilities. English language teachers and practitioners have already proved debating as an effective technique in teaching English which is a strong source of motivation for EFL teachers who are yet to use debate in their classes.” [5]

Result and Discussion

It is clear that debating in English is a practice that calls for all English language skills alongside the skills of presentation and delivery. Debaters need updated data about cutting-edge issues and ideas of various fields. What's more, they need to conduct research on different issues. While presenting their argument and logic, debaters require standard delivery skills to persuade judges and audiences. While practicing in an EFL lesson, debating makes students use language and presentation skills.

The student who is involved in this form at the preparation stage, simulates the game, and in subsequent stages acts inside the structure, inside the created form, inside the invented rules and procedures. This process greatly enhances the responsibility of participants, since designed means of thinking covers a wider contact field of interaction: from equipping a personal position to forms of communication.

Debate method requires significant intellectual and emotional stress. From this point of view, it is important to create a positive emotional atmosphere in the team, whose members have entered into an argument. Entering into a dispute, students have the opportunity to show their erudition in various fields of knowledge, the acquisition of social experience, the level of possession of moral values, beliefs. Therefore, participants of the debate technique have the opportunity to affirm their position in the team, to rise one more step of social maturity. It is essential that all students participate in the preparation and conduct the debate. Through the usage of debate, pupils can easily avert being scared of communication in English. Moreover, if they practice regularly, they are able to boost up their pronunciation, fluency and vocabulary.

Conclusion

In conclusion, debates develop students' skills, which are necessary for an effective communication in any area of human activity, develop critical thinking, being

at the same time a popular form of intellectual pastime. Participation in the debate provides an opportunity for developing the ability to work in a team, the ability to concentrate on the essence of the problem and defend uncommon solutions. Debate prepares pupils for responsible decision making, to be an independent and for other skills which are necessary in a society.

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